

Studies in the Anthraquinone Series.

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Among the hydroxy-anthraquinones occurring in nature, there is only one which is known to contain a carbinol group, namely Aloe-emodin (1:8-dihydroxy-anthraquinone-3-carbinol). On account of the well-known physiological properties of this substance, it appeared to us to be of interest to prepare and study the properties of other hydroxy-anthraquinone-carbinols of the same type but containing a smaller number of hydroxyl groups. In this connection, we have prepared 1-hydroxyanthraquinone-6-carboxylic acid and 1-hydroxyanthraquinone-6 carbinol and also 1-hydroxyanthraquinone-3-carboxylic acid and 1-hydroxyanthraquinone-3-carbinol.

The therapeutic properties of the substances have not yet been studied

1-Hydroxy-6-methyl-anthraquinone (Mitter and Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 619), was acetylated and the acetyl derivative was oxidised by chromic acid in a solution of glacial acetic acid and acetic anhydride (Fischer, Falco and Gross; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1911, ii, 83, 208) whereby 1-hydroxyanthraquinone-6-carboxylic acid was obtained after deacetylation. The acid was re-acetylated and then converted into the acid chloride by treatment with thionyl chloride. The acid chloride was reduced to the aldehyde by passing a slow stream of pure and dry hydrogen through a solution of the substance in pure xylene at 130-40° in presence of palladiumised barium sulphate and on hydrolysis 1-hydroxy-6-aldehydo-anthraquinone was obtained. (Rosenmund, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 585; Rosenmund and Zetzche, *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 425, Mitter and Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 375).

The aldehyde was next reduced catalytically by means of hydrogen in presence of platinum oxide with ferrous chloride as promoter when 1-hydroxyanthraquinone-6-carbinol was obtained. (Roger Adams and co-workers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1937; 1923, 45, 2171;

1924, 46, 1675; Mitter and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*)

1-Hydroxy-3-methyl anthraquinone was prepared according to the method of Bentley, Gardner and Weizmann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1626), and acetylated with acetic anhydride in presence of a drop of strong sulphuric acid. The product was then oxidised with chromic acid (Fischer, Falco and Gross, *loc. cit.*). During subsequent operations the acetyl group was partially knocked off and it was found necessary to de-acetylate it completely with alcoholic potash and to reacetylate with acetic anhydride in presence of a drop of sulphuric acid. The conversion of the acetylated acid into the corresponding chloride and its subsequent reduction into aldehyde and alcohol followed exactly the lines of 1-acetoxy-anthraquinone-6-carboxylic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(WITH SATINDRAJIBAN DAS-GUPTA).

1-Acetoxy-6-methyl-anthraquinone. — 1-Hydroxy-6-methyl-anthraquinone prepared according to the method of Mitter and Sarkar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 619) was treated with acetic anhydride and a few drops of strong sulphuric acid, the mixture warmed until a clear solution was obtained and allowed to stand for some time when

the acetyl derivative separated. The mixture was then poured into water, filtered and the residue crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 172°. The compound was previously obtained by Mitter and Sarkar (*loc. cit.*) but no experimental details were given.

1-Hydroxy anthraquinone-6-carboxylic acid.—1-Acetoxy-6-methyl-anthraquinone (2 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of acetic anhydride (35 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (35 c.c.) and the solution heated on a water-bath at 60°. A chromic acid mixture was prepared by dissolving 4 g. of the acid in the least possible quantity of water and diluting with a mixture of 20 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 20 c.c. of acetic anhydride. The oxidising mixture was added, 5 c.c. at a time, in rapid succession, to the above solution with occasional shaking. The mixture was kept at 60° for one hour and then heated at 100° on the water bath for another hour. Acetic acid and acetic anhydride were completely removed by distilling the mixture under reduced pressure and the residue boiled with moderately concentrated hydrochloric acid for about half an hour and then diluted with water and allowed to cool. The filtered and washed residue was slightly warmed with 5 % sodium carbonate solution, the extract acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate filtered, washed and dried. Bright yellow needles from pyridine, m.p. 297°, yield nearly theoretical. (Found: C, 67.32; H, 3.37. $C_{15}H_8O_5$ requires C, 67.16; H, 2.98 per cent).

1-Acetoxy-anthraquinone-6-carboxylic acid chloride.—The acid was acetylated as in the case of the anthraquinone. Light yellow needles from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 242°. (Found: C, 66.16; H, 2.85. $C_{17}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 65.80; H, 3.19 per cent). The acetylated product was refluxed with 25 to 30 times its weight of thionyl chloride on a water-bath for 2-3 hours when a clear solution was obtained and no hydrochloric acid could be detected at the mouth of the guard tube fitted at the mouth of the condenser. Thionyl chloride was completely removed by distilling under reduced pressure and the residue crystallised from benzene as yellow crystals, m.p. 182°. (Found: Cl, 11.51. $C_{17}H_9O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 10.80 per cent).

1-Hydroxy-6-aldehydo-anthraquinone.—0.4 G. of the acetylated acid chloride and 0.2 g. of the palladiumised barium sulphate (Rosenmund, *loc. cit.*) was introduced into a flask containing 25 c.c. of very pure and dry xylene and provided with a side tube and an upright condenser. Hydrogen gas generated in a Kipp's apparatus from pure zinc and sulphuric acid was purified and dried by passing successively

through AgNO_3 solution, KMnO_4 solution, KOH solution, concentrated sulphuric acid, and finally phosphorus pentoxide and passed through the mixture at the rate of one to two bubbles per second while the flask was maintained at $130-40^\circ$. The open end of the condenser was fitted with a calcium chloride guard tube.

The reaction was completed in about 2 hours when hydrochloric acid gas could scarcely be detected at the end of the guard tube. The contents of the flask were then filtered, the filtrate shaken with 50 c.c. of 10% sodium bisulphite solution in a mechanical shaker and the aqueous layer separated and boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid for about half an hour when the aldehyde was precipitated. Brown needles from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 194° , yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 71.02; H, 2.81. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.42; H, 3.17 per cent).

1-Hydroxyanthraquinone-6-carbinol.—0.1 G. of platinum oxide catalyst (Roger Adams and others, *loc. cit.*) 0.2 g. of the aldehyde, sodium ethoxide equivalent to 0.36 c.c. of a millimolar solution and ferrous chloride equivalent to 0.5 c.c. of a 0.2 molar solution were introduced in the order given into a clean and dry hydrogenating flask, 150 c.c. of absolute alcohol introduced and the flask evacuated by means of a water pump until the alcohol began to boil. The flask was then connected with the hydrogenation apparatus and the gas introduced while the flask was mechanically shaken until there was no further absorption of hydrogen. The absorption was complete in about 10 minutes. The contents of the flask were filtered and the filtrate distilled under diminished pressure to remove the alcohol and the residue crystallised first from 50% acetic acid and then from toluene when orange needles were obtained, m.p. $160-62^\circ$. (Found: C, 70.98; H, 3.88. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 70.86; H, 3.93 per cent).

(WITH SUMATICHAND BACHHWAT).

1-Acetoxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone.—Sharp pale yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 156° . (Found: C, 72.6; H, 4.3. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.8; H, 4.3 per cent).

1-Hydroxyanthraquinone-3-carboxylic acid.—Yellow woolly needles from pyridine or glacial acetic acid, m.p. $282-84^\circ$. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 3.5. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_8\text{O}_5$ requires C, 67.1; H, 3.0 per cent).

1-Acetoxy-anthraquinone-3-carboxylic acid.—Greenish yellow silky needles from acetic acid, m.p. 276° . (Found: C, 65.9; H, 3.2. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 65.8; H, 3.2 per cent).

1-Acetoxy-anthraquinone-3-carboxylic acid chloride.—Pale yellow micro-crystals from benzene, m.p. 162-63°. (Found: Cl, 10.2. $C_{17}H_9O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 10.8 per cent).

1-Hydroxyanthraquinone-3-aldehyde.—The temperature was maintained at 140-45° for 3-4 hours and then at 148° for another 2 hours while the current of hydrogen was increased. At the end of about 6 hours from the beginning of the operation, no hydrochloric acid could be detected at the mouth of the guard tube. Dark brown needles from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 214° (with sublimation). (Found: C, 72.0; H, 3.20. $C_{15}H_8O_4$ requires C, 71.4; H, 3.17 per cent).

1-Hydroxyanthraquinone-3-carbinol.—0.2 G. of 1-hydroxy-anthraquinone-3-aldehyde was introduced into the reduction flask with 0.1 g. of platinum oxide, 0.36 millimole of sodium ethoxide and 0.1 millimole of ferrous chloride and absolute alcohol, just sufficient to dissolve the aldehyde. The reduction was complete in 5-10 minutes. The mass left after the removal of alcohol was first crystallised from dilute acetic acid. On further crystallisation from toluene, orange needles were obtained, m.p. 197-99°. (Found: C, 70.7; H, 3.96. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.9; H, 3.93 per cent).

